

Paper 23

**A STUDY ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION
TOWARDS SNAP DEAL**

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ABSTRACT

The rapid development of the internet has strongly impact upon the worldwide marketing environment. Currently it has become one of the popular approaches for business and customer to perform trade over the internet. Businesses have been coming up with creative ways to promote their product via online. Thus it describes how modern market is replacing the traditional markets. This study is taking place to identify the factors that may influence customer's online shopping satisfaction. Generally, the success of online shopping essentially depends on the customer satisfaction during their purchase. Online shopping has created a revolution for consumers, growing rapidly year by year and offering a golden age of shopping. We've changed the way we go shopping. In just a decade online shopping – buying goods on the internet – has gone from being virtually non-existent to become worth billions of pounds each year. Books, CD's, clothes, electronics, we go shopping online for them all, without ever leaving our living rooms. These days we take shopping online for granted, an adoption that's happened remarkably quickly. We can even order groceries online with delivery the next day – if needs be we don't need to set foot out of our homes! The present research paper focuses on the consumer behaviour and perceptions of customers towards the services rendered by different online marketers.

Keywords

Online shopping, customer's perceptions, customer satisfaction, study.

Executive summary

The technology is changing so fast with online shopping. It has observed that last two decade the online purchase has increased significantly. Now online purchase is feels like a purchase of fast moving consuming item. Which signifies that the people are very much interested in doing online shopping in their day to day activities? The online shopping is the main source among the people. As described in this article, a set of dimensions can be identified in the literature, which can be used to characterise and differentiate the various perspectives on consumer research.

Introduction

Snap deal is an online market place located at New Delhi, India. The company was started by 'Kunal Bahl', Wharton graduate as part of the dual degree M&T engineering and business program at Penn and Rohit Bansal, An alumnus of IIT Delhi in February 2010.

Snapdeal.com was started in February 2010 as a daily deals platform inspired by Groupon.com but expanded in September 2011 to become an online marketplace. Snap deal has grown to become one of the largest online marketplace in India offering an assortment of 4 million+ products across diverse categories from over 50,000 sellers, shipping to 4,000 towns and cities in India. In March 2015, snap deal brought Amir Khan for the promotion of its website in India.

Description

Name of the company is Snap deal, it is a private type of company, and it was founded in 2010. Company's headquarters is at New Delhi, Kunal Bahl is the founder of the company. It is served in the industry of internet, services provided is E-commerce. Employees are 2000+. Bachatey Rahol is the slogan of the company, there 20 million users and per minute company gets 5 orders. For more details can follow the website i.e. www.snapdeal.com.

Objectives

- To find whether the customers are satisfied with the mode of payment.
- To know how far the customers are benefited with the easy return facility.
- To know the aggregate percentage of people who prefer online shopping.
- To evaluate whether the online shopping is safe.
- To recognize the most preferable shopping site.
- To determine the most frequently purchased products.
- To evaluate when the people prefer to shop online.
- To know whether online shopping price is less than traditional shopping price.

Research Methodology

The research methodology used is descriptive research which includes primary and secondary data. The sample size chooses are 150 customers of Snap deal. Our survey is based on questionnaire method.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Depicting the customers views regarding Snap deal

1. How disappointed would you be if you could no longer use our company?

How disappointed would you be if you could no longer use our company?

(174 responses)

When we consider the survey we came to know that 52.9% are quite disappointed, 22.4% are moderately, 12.1% are extremely, 6.9% are not at all, and some percentage of people are slightly disappointed if they could no longer use our company.

2. Overall how satisfied or dissatisfied are you with our company?

Overall how satisfied or dissatisfied are you with our company?

(173 responses)

According survey we come to know that 69.9% people are somewhat satisfied, 15.6% are neither satisfied or dissatisfied, 9.8% people are very satisfied, some are somewhat dissatisfied and some percentage of people are very dissatisfied with our company.

3. Which of the following words would you use to describe our products?

Which of the following words would you use to describe our products?

(173 responses)

These shows the various descriptions towards products i.e. 41.6% are useful, 28.9% are high quality, 12.7% are reliable and others are unique and good value of money.

4. How well do our products meet your needs?

How well do our products meet your needs?

(173 responses)

Here it tells that 54.3% are very well, 31.8% are somewhat well, and 7.5% are extremely well our products meet the customer needs, but little percentage of customers tells that our product is not at all well in meeting their needs.

5. How would you rate the quality of the product?

How would you rate the quality of the product??

(173 responses)

According to survey we came to know that how did customers rate the quality of product, 64.2% are high quality, and 24.3% are neither high nor low quality, 6.9% are of very high quality nor few percentages are of low quality product.

6. How would you rate the value for money of the product?

How would you rate the value for money of the product??

(174 responses)

By doing the survey we came to know that 54.6% rated average, 32.2% rated above average, 6.9% rated excellent and few people rated below average and poor.

7. How responsive have we been to your questions or concerns about our products?

How responsive have we been to your questions or concerns about our products?

(174 responses)

Snap deal is very responsive towards customers. 67.8% people say that snap deal is very responsive, 15.5% people say that snap deal is not so responsive, 10.9% people say it is extremely responsive and according to 5.7% people it is not at all responsive.

8. How long have you been a customer of our company?

How long have you been a customer of our company?

(176 responses)

Here we can find various views of the customers regarding their purchase.

9. How likely are you to purchase any of our products again?

How likely are You to purchase any of our products again?

(174 responses)

This are the various views regarding customers likes and dislikes of purchase any of our products again, 58.6% people are very likely to do the purchase again and some percentage of people are not at all likely to do the purchase again.

10. How likely is it that you would recommend this to a friend or colleague?

How likely is it that you would recommend this to a friend or colleague?

(170 responses)

59.4% people are likely to recommend, 30% people are somewhat okay with recommending and few are i.e. 10.6% are not so interested in recommending our company.

Findings

- Most of the people are satisfied with the mode of payment.
- Easy return facilities are enjoyed by most of the people.
- Even today majority of the people prefer traditional way of shopping.

- Due to privacy policies provided, almost all the customers feel safe while shopping online.
- Customers feel that products are delivered to them on time.
- Customers most frequently purchase clothes, footwear's and electronics from online.

From the above findings/observation here are some suggestions

- Since some of the products which is delivered differ from what it is displayed.
- Instalment payment facility can be provided to attract and increase the tendency of shopping especially at the time offers and discounts.
- Size of the products should be properly displayed by the online sellers.

Conclusion

Of course, online shopping won't ever completely eliminate its physical counterpart. There are still areas where we prefer to go into a shop and select items – they're part of any community, from news agents to supermarkets. But there is no going back, and online shopping will become an even more central part of our lives, growing more sophisticated with each passing year.

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